

Synthesis of 5:6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic Acid and of some Monomethoxy- homophthalic Acids.

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During the course of our synthetical experiments on ψ -opianic acid and berberine alkaloids we required some hydrindones and homophthalic acids as the starting substances. Careful study of the literature revealed the fact that a majority of the monomethoxyhomophthalic acids and 5:6-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid are still unknown. In this paper the synthesis of 5:6-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (I) and 4- and 5-methoxyhomophthalic acids (III, II) is recorded. The synthesis of 3- and 6-methoxyhomophthalic acids is reserved for a future communication.

5:6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid was synthesised in the following manner: *o*-Veratraldehyde was first converted into 2:3-dimethoxycinnamic acid according to the conditions described before (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 223). The cinnamic acid was then reduced and converted according to the method of Ruheman (*Ber.*, 1920, 83, 275) into 4:5-dimethoxyhydrindone (IV), the isonitroso derivative of which was converted into 2-carboxy-5:6-dimethoxyphenylacetonitrile (VII) in a yield of about 95% by the action of toluene-*p*-sulphonyl chloride. The cyanide was hydrolysed to 5:6-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid in an yield of about 90%. This acid was also obtained in a poorer yield by the direct oxidation of 4:5-dimethoxyhydrindone (IV) with dichromate and sulphuric

acid. During the course of these experiments 4:5-dimethoxy-1:2-diketohydrindene (VI), m.p. 150°, was also isolated.

5-Methoxyhomophthalic acid (II) which had previously been obtained by Ingold and Pigott (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1503) has now been prepared in a better yield by the application of the above method. 5-Methoxy-1:2-diketohydrindene (VIII), m.p. 152° was also isolated.

4-Methoxyhomophthalic acid was also prepared by a method similar to that outlined above. 6-Methoxyhydrindone (X) was first prepared by Ingold and Pigott (*loc. cit.*) starting from 6-nitrohydrindone. Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1081) were unable to isolate this hydrindone by the action of aluminium chloride upon *p*-methoxyhydrocinnamoyl chloride (IX). We have now succeeded in converting the acid chloride directly into 6-methoxy-

hydrindone by the action of aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene solution in an yield of about 20%.

6-Methoxyhydrindone (X) was then converted into the isonitroso compound and the latter into 4-methoxy-2-carboxyphenylacetonitrile which was smoothly hydrolysed to 4-methoxyhomophthalic acid (III).

EXPERIMENTAL.

4:5-Dimethoxyhydrindone was prepared according to the directions given by Ruhemann (*loc. cit.*). It was converted into the isonitroso derivative in the usual manner.

4:5-Dimethoxy-1:2-diketohydrindene.—The isonitrosohydrindone (10 g.) was mixed with formaldehyde (20 c.c. of 40 %) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) and heated to incipient boiling while being stirred. The isonitroso compound passed into solution and the diketohydrindene separated as a crystalline powder. The heating was continued for half an hour, the mixture cooled and diluted with water. The precipitated substance was collected, washed well with water and dried on the water-bath. It crystallised from benzene as yellow powder, m.p. 150° (decomp.). (Found: C, 63.9; H, 4.9. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

4:5-Dimethoxyindenoquinoxaline.—1:2-Diketo-5:6-dimethoxyhydrindene (1 g.) and *o*-phenylenediamine (0.5 g.) were dissolved in hot ethyl alcohol. The crystalline product obtained on cooling the solution recrystallised from ethyl alcohol in slender needles, m.p. 192°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73.4; H, 5.0 per cent).

2-Carboxy-5:6-dimethoxyphenylacetonitrile.—4:5-Dimethoxyisonitrosohydrindone (5 g.) dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide (53 c.c. of 10 %) was treated gradually with toluene-*p*-sulphonyl chloride (7 g.), solution being completed by heating the mixture on the steam-bath for 10 minutes. The cooled solution was filtered and the filtrate acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid, when the carboxynitrile separated, yield 95%. It crystallised from

dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 175° . (Found: C, 59.9; H, 5.2. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 59.7; H, 5.0 per cent).

5:6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid.—The nitrile described above (10 g.) was hydrolysed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (100 c.c. of 10 %) for 5 hours on a sand-bath. The cooled solution was filtered and the filtrate acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid, when 5:6-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid was precipitated in a yield of 90 %. It is sparingly soluble in cold water but fairly easily soluble in boiling water from which it crystallised in long needles, melting at 196° . (Found: C, 54.7; H, 5.2. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 55.0; H, 5.0 per cent).

5-Methoxy-1-hydrindone was prepared according to the method of Ingold and Pigott (*loc. cit.*).

5-Methoxy-isonitrosohydrindone.—The ketone (5 g.) dissolved in methyl alcohol (15 c.c.) was mixed with freshly distilled isoamyl nitrite (7 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) and the mixture maintained at 50° for half an hour with vigorous stirring. The isonitrosohydrindone separated in almost quantitative yield. It crystallised from alcohol in beautiful yellow needles, m.p. 221° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.9; H, 4.6. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7 per cent).

5-Methoxy-1:2-diketohydrindene was prepared from the isonitrosohydrindone similarly as 4:5-dimethoxydiketohydrindene. It crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 152° . (Found: C, 67.8; H, 4.8. $C_{10}H_8O_3$ requires C, 68.1; H, 4.5 per cent).

5-Methoxyindenoquinoxaline was prepared in the same manner as 4:5-dimethoxyindenoquinoxaline and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 140° . (Found: C, 77.4; H, 4.9. $C_{16}H_{12}ON_2$ requires C, 77.4; H, 4.8 per cent).

2-Carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetonitrile was prepared similarly as 2-carboxy-5:6-dimethoxyphenylacetonitrile, the yield being nearly quantitative. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 177° . (Found: C, 62.6; H, 5.0. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7 per cent).

5-Methoxyhomophthalic acid.—This acid has been prepared by Ingold and Pigott (*loc. cit.*) by the direct oxidation of 5-methoxyhydrindone with chromic acid. It is obtained more conveniently and in a better yield by the hydrolysis of 2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetonitrile, m.p. 222° , yield 90 %.

6-Methoxyhydrindone.—This ketone has been prepared by Ingold and Pigott (*loc. cit.*) from the corresponding 6-nitrohydrindone

through the amino and hydroxy derivatives. Perkin and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) state that it is not formed in any appreciable amount by the action of aluminium chloride upon *p*-methoxyhydrocinnamoyl chloride and that it is formed in very small quantities by the action of P_2O_5 on the *p*-methoxyhydrocinnamic acid in benzene solution. After a series of experiments, it was found that 6-methoxyhydrindone could be directly prepared from *p*-methoxyhydrocinnamic acid in a yield of about 20% under the following conditions:— Aluminium chloride (10 g.) dissolved in nitrobenzene (50 c.c.) was gradually added during half an hour to a solution of *p*-methoxy- β -phenylpropionyl chloride (10 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) (under cooling) and the whole allowed to remain overnight. The reaction product was decomposed with water and then subjected to steam distillation, when nitrobenzene first distilled over and then pure 6-methoxyhydrindone, m.p. 109° . It crystallised from alcohol in long needles, m.p. 109° .

6-Methoxyisonitrosohydrindone, prepared similarly as 5-methoxyisonitrosohydrindone, crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 234° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.5; H, 4.9. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7 per cent).

6-Methoxydiketohydrindene is very soluble in the ordinary organic solvents and crystallised from ether in yellow plates, m.p. 126° . (Found: C, 68.0; H, 4.8. $C_{10}H_8O_3$ requires C, 68.1; H, 4.5 per cent).

6-Methoxyindenoquinoxaline crystallised from alcohol in silky needles, m.p. 156° . (Found: C, 77.4; H, 4.9. $C_{16}H_{12}ON_2$ requires C, 77.4; H, 4.8 per cent).

4-Methoxy-2-carboxyphenylacetonitrile was prepared similarly as the isomeric 5-methoxy compound. It is more soluble in methyl alcohol than its isomer and crystallised in small needles, m.p. 140° . (Found: C, 62.6; H, 5.0. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7 per cent).

4-Methoxyhomophthalic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the above nitrile with aqueous sodium hydroxide and acidifying the alkaline liquid with concentrated hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from water in small needles, m.p. 188° . (Found: C, 57.5; H, 5.0. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

